

Optimisation Route Value Comparison of Cataract Implant Lenses of PT XYZ by Saving Matrix Method and Cluster First Route Second Method to Select Hospitals in West Java and DKI Jakarta

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to obtain the most accurate and optimal route of cataract implant lenses distribution to minimise distribution costs and to find out the maximum extent of cost saving possible. The population in this research is obtained from company data in the pharmaceutical industry located at Padalarang and the sample for this research is the data for the demand of lenses from select hospitals in West Java and DKI Jakarta. Determination of the distribution route is analysed by using the Saving Matrix method and Cluster First Route Second method. Results of the Saving Matrix method analysis shows that the initial total distance of the distribution route of 4256 kilometers can be reduced to 1551.5 kilometers, reducing the distance by 64.09% and by using the Cluster First Route Second method. Initial cost of Rp.18.843.200 went down to Rp. 8.873.925 using the Saving Matrix method and Rp. 8.851.790 with the Cluster First Route Second method. The savings gained are 52.90 % and 53.02 % respectively.

Keywords: *Saving Matrix, Cluster First Route Second, Transportation Cost, Efficiency.*

INTRODUCTION

The eye is a vital sense for humans, through them, humans absorb visual information that is used to carry out various activities. But vision impairment, or partial loss of it, happens often, ranging from minor inconveniences to major impairment that can lead to blindness. (Virgo, 2020). Cataract, lens turbidity, is one of the common reasons of vision impairment, with estimations of up to 16 million people affected worldwide (Penny A Asbell et al, 2005).

World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that the number of people affected by visual impairment worldwide is 1,3 billion people. Cataract is the second-most reason of visual impairment (33%) after uncorrected refractive error (42%). However, cataract is the leading cause of blindness with a prevalence of 51% (WHO, 2014).

Indonesian citizens tend to suffer from cataract 15 years earlier compared to other citizens of subtropical nations at 16-22% cataract sufferers that underwent surgery under the age of 55. Prevalence of cataract data in the province of West Java and DKI Jakarta from the results of enumerator officers are 1.5% and 0.9% (KemenKes, 2014).

Until a research comes up and proves otherwise, the only effective way known to reduce the risk of cataract is to reduce the exposure of UV-B radiation on the eyes and to stop smoking. (Garry Brian, 2001)

Cataract surgery is a simple surgical procedure to remove lens turbidity on the affected eye by replacing it with clear lens from an artificial eye. This purpose of this implantable eyepiece replacement is to rectify sharpness of vision, phacoemulsification and extracapsular manual small incision surgery achieve excellent visual result with minor complications, but extracapsular manual small incision surgery is significantly faster, cheaper, and requires less technology. Therefore, extracapsular manual small incision surgery might be the suitable choice of cataract surgery in developing countries. (Tabin, Chen, & Espandar, 2008)

PT XYZ is one of the many lens manufacturing company that caters to hospitals in Indonesia, where the products are distributed through a Distribution Centre (DC) to the destination hospital.

PT XYZ is a manufacturer and distribution hub for lenses in and out of the country. Almost 25% of the product cost is spent on distribution, hence evaluation to improve distribution method efficiency is carried out from time to time. (Masudin, 2014). One of the most vital operational decision in distribution management is the schedule and delivery route from one location to multiple destinations. Decision of the delivery schedule and route of each vehicle will greatly affect the distribution cost. (Hasibuan, 2021). The purpose of this research is to determine the optimal route of cataract implant lensed using the Saving Matrix method and Cluster First Route Second method. Benefits of this research journal is:

1. Obtaining the most optimal route of distribution between both methods used.
2. A first step into further research of comparing every distribution method to obtain the method with the highest optimal value.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Distribution

In the Oxford Dictionary, distribution is defined as the way that something is spread or exists over a particular area or among a group of people; the system of transporting and delivering a product (Oxford Learner's Dictionary, 2021). Moreover, distribution can be defined as a group of companies and individuals that take over the rights or assist in transferring rights of a property or service from a producer to consumers (Kotler, 2004).

Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP)

Vehicle Routing Problem (VRP) is a problem in a distribution system that aims to create an optimal route for a group of vehicles with known capacities in order to fulfill consumer demands where the number of demand and location is known. In a distribution activity, the most important factors are the route to be taken, number of fleets that will be utilized, route balancing and minimalizing customer complaints are vital steps to be taken if a company wants to suppress transportation costs (Toth, 2002). The result of a VRP is a number of customer demand distribution route where a vehicle leaves the DC (Distribution Center) towards the customer and back.

Scientist (Wright, 1964), furthers this research and succeeded in creating a method called the Saving Matrix method, along with the industrial world development. Since then, the development of VRP continues to grow as it plays a significant role in the distribution process of the industrial world.

Nearest Neighbour Method

Nearest Neighbour method is an algorithm that has a rule that it always goes to the nearest unvisited customer with the least distance while observing several constraints. The following are the steps taken in the route development using the Nearest Neighbor method:

1. Setting the DC (Distribution Center) as the initial delivery point.
2. Determining the destination with the shortest distance from the DC, then combining both points.
3. The last visited destination becomes the initial delivery point, the next point is the shortest point from the initial delivery point.
4. Do this process repetitively until the vehicle capacity is insufficient to continue delivery.
5. Drag the destination along a line, this line is the route taken one-way, with the vehicle capacity as a constraint in developing a delivery route.
6. Do the same process from the first step to the last.

Saving Matrix Method

Saving Matrix method is a method used to determine the distance, route, time, or costs in carrying out a product distribution from a company to the customer. This method aims to ensure production aligns with the customer's need effectively and efficiently so as the company can save on cost, labor, and distribution time. (Instantiningrum, 2010). The steps in a saving matrix method (Instantiningrum, 2010) are as follows:

1. Determining the distance matrix
Determination of distance matrix is based on the data of distance between the origin and the destination, from the destination to the next destination, as well as final destination that returns to the origin that is calculated by using the formula below:

$$j(1,2) = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2}$$

Where:

j = distance between facility 1 and 2

x = x coordinate

y = y coordinate

However, if the distance between two coordinates are known, the calculation using the above formula is not used; the known distance between the two coordinates is used instead.

2. Determining the saving matrix
Determination of the saving matrix is carried out by combining the distribution for a location that will be passed by one truck exclusively. Therefore, there will be savings to be gained if a route is merged with another that is deemed to be of the same route. To calculate the saving matrix, the formula below can be used:

$$S(x, y) = j(x, y) + j(x, y) - j(x, y)$$

Where:

S = distance saved (merging of routes x and y)

3. Route and vehicle allocation
Vehicle allocation to a route where a new delivery route is determined by means of a route merger.
4. Sorting of destinations in a route
To sort destinations in a route to determine a distribution route, several methods can be utilized, such as:
 1. Nearest Insert method
Prioritizing locations that; when inserted to an existing route, produces the shortest distance.
 2. Nearest Neighbor method
This method determines the destination by using the shortest distance with the final destination. The advantage of this method is that it has a shorter iteration and gives the optimal result to solve optimization problems such that distribution using this method can be used as an initial route and improved upon further later using other methods.

Cluster First Route Second method

The recommend approach to solve complex problems, are two methods: the sweep method and the more complex and accurate savings method. (Wardhana). Cluster First Route Second is a part of the sweep method in the VRP variant. Solutions using this method is done by creating a cluster of destinations first, then creating a route. (Benoit Crevier, 2007).

The steps in the solving of a VRP with this method are as follows: (Ballou, 2005):

1. Plot all destination location and depot location on a map.
2. Create a cluster by dragging a line on the map to wherever from a depot, then rotate this line until it intersects with a destination location. The rotation direction can be clockwise or counter-clockwise.
3. Everytime it intersects a destination location, evaluate the vehicle capacity whether or not if the destination location is inserted into the cluster, still fulfills the vehicle capacity. If it does not, then the clustering process has to be stopped and continued by creating a new cluster where the destination location is not in any cluster.
4. Then, after all the destination locations has been inserted into its own clusters, schedule a delivery in each cluster to the destination location. This scheduling is done is done until the shortest total distance of each cluster is found.

METHOD

The steps undertaken in this research are as follows:

1. Literature review
Literature review is done by gathering references from papers, books, and other researches related to the research material.
2. Field study
Field study is carried out by using data from PT XYZ, cataract lens product distribution data from the West Java and DKI Jakarta regions that are centered in PT XYZ. Data used are the delivery in the month of April 2021 that amounts to 19 data.
3. Problem Formulation
How to determine the optimal distribution route for the distribution of cataract implant lenses of PT XYZ.
4. Research Purpose
Determining the optimal route by using the Saving Matrix and Cluster First-Route Second method.
5. Data Collection
Data used in this research is secondary data taken from PT XYZ's PPIC, that covers cataract implant lenses distribution data in the West Java and DKI Jakarta Region.
6. Data Processing
The data collected is processed to determine the minimum value from each method that is the Saving Matrix and Cluster First-Route Second method.
7. Data Analysis
The data obtained produces the utilization of maximum vehicle capacity, total route, and shortest distance.
8. Conclusion
A conclusion is made to answer the research purpose based on the research results that has been carried out. Suggestions made by the author are input on how to improve and recognize flaws in this research.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Data processing is carried out by gathering the lens demand data from select hospitals in West Java and DKI Jakarta. One box contains 100 lenses, distribution is carried out by a truck fleet with the following specifications:

	Type	Mitsubitsi Colt Diesel
	Fuel Consumption	1 liter/10 km
	Fuel	Dexlite
	Capacity	123 box
*fuel consumption efficiency: 1 liter for 10 km		

Figure 1. Fleet Specification

Based on the data gathered, the following list comprises of the hospital name, distance, and total demand. Origin used is a Distribution Center Office located in Padalarang, West where the distance was obtained using *Google Maps*, the data can be seen as in Table 1:

Table 1. Cataract Lens Demand List from Select Hospitals

No.	Lists of Hospital	Region	Demand	Demand Box	Distance (Km)
1	RS Mata Cicendo	Bandung	3230	32	14
2	RS Mata Bandung Eye Center	Bandung	3415	34	19
3	Netra Klinik Spesialis Mata	Bandung	3672	37	16
4	Klinik Utama Mata JEC	Bekasi	4222	42	116
5	Klinik Utama Mata JEC	Cibubur	3876	39	142
6	Klini Mata SMEC	Bekasi	2550	26	113
7	Klinik Mata dr. Hasri Ainun Habibie	Bogor	4313	43	109
8	RS Bogor Eya Center	Bogor	3569	36	129
9	RS Islam Assyifa	Sukabumi	6987	70	79
10	RS Restu Kasih	Jakarta Timur	2991	30	134
11	Mitra Keluarga	Kemayoran	4554	46	148
12	RS Premier	Jatinegara	3071	31	143
13	Mayapada Hospital	Jakarta Selatan	2339	23	138
14	RS Tebet	Tebet	1977	20	139
15	RS Mata JEC	Menteng	1545	15	149
16	KMN Eyecare	Kebon Jeruk	3888	39	116
17	Siloam Hospital TB Simatupang	Cilandak	2893	29	138
18	Siloam Hospital Asri	Pancoran	3678	37	138
19	Ciputra SMG Eye Clinic	Setiabudi	5195	52	148

The hospital locations are spread across West Java and DKI Jakarta, the cost incurred by the company each month is Rp. 18.843.200 to deliver cataract lenses to the select hospitals with 19 distribution routes and a mileage of 4256.

Route development using the Saving Matrix and Nearest Neighbor Method

Following is the distance matrix between each node, where the destination node is the select hospitals and the origin is the distribution center office.

Table 2. Distance Matrix

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	
0		14	19	16	116	142	113	109	129	79	134	148	143	138	139	149	116	138	138	148	
1			7.6	4.6	129	155	134	183	164	98	141	151	145	153	143	149	156	153	146	147	
2				5.9	136	162	143	190	171	105	148	158	150	161	150	157	165	160	154	154	
3					131	136	136	134	154	101	156	169	162	162	160	168	162	161	161	149	
4						34	6.7	62	43	111	20	30	22	32	22	29	38	32	26	26	
5								30	34	16	91	20	35	25	25	25	30	38	24	24	29
6									63	45	120	22	16	17	35	21	19	28	35	25	21
7										21	64	44	62	49	39	54	56	53	39	50	54
8											61	42	57	47	47	48	53	60	47	47	52
9												98	111	103	105	102	109	115	102	102	106
10													17	7.2	15	6.8	12	21	14	6	11
11														10	32	18	8.3	15	32	20	17
12															26	6.2	5.8	20	25	8.2	8.1
13																14	17	19	1	9.9	14
14																	14	19	22	7.5	9.1
15																		10	16	8.7	7.1
16																			19	14	12
17																				11	15
18																					5.1
19																					

After obtaining the distance matrix value from each node and origin, a calculation has to be made in order to find out how much saving is gained when several distribution nodes are merged. Saving value is obtained by using the following formula:

Table 3. Distance Savings Formula

Condition	Distance	
Before Optimization	$O_i + O_j$	$2 \times (O_i) + 2 \times (O_j)$
After Optimization	O_{ij}	$(O_i) + (i_j) + (O_j)$
Comparison of Distance	S_{ij}	$(O_i) + (O_j) - (i_j)$

From the above formula, a distance saving matrix is obtained:

Table 4. Saving Matrix Distance

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
1		25	25	1	1	-7	-60	-21	-5	7	11	14	-1	10	14	-26	-1	6	15
2			29	-1	-1	-9	-62	-23	-7	5	9	12	-4	8	11	-28	-3	3	13
3				1	22	-7	-9	-9	-6	-6	-5	-3	-8	-5	-3	-30	-7	-7	15
4					224	222	163	202	84	230	234	237	222	233	236	194	222	228	238
5						225	217	255	130	256	255	260	255	256	261	220	256	256	261
6							159	197	72	225	245	239	216	231	243	201	216	226	240
7								217	124	199	195	203	208	194	202	172	208	197	203
8									147	221	220	225	220	220	225	185	220	220	225
9										115	116	119	114	116	119	80	115	115	121
10											265	270	257	266	271	229	258	266	271
11												281	254	269	289	249	254	266	279
12													255	276	286	239	256	273	283
13														263	270	235	275	266	272
14															274	236	255	270	278
15																255	271	278	290
16																	235	240	252
17																		265	271
18																			281
19																			

The following is the sequence of nodes, based on the calculation result, demand, and distance traveled from each node:

Table 5. Chosen Nodes

Route	Node	Demand	Total Demand
1	15	15	113
	19	52	
	11	46	
2	12	31	120
	18	37	
	13	23	
	17	29	
3	14	20	115
	10	30	
	5	39	
	6	26	
4	16	39	117
	4	42	
	8	36	
5	7	43	113
	9	70	
6	3	37	103
	2	34	
	1	32	

The following is the route development using the nearest neighbor algorithm:

Table 6. Nearest neighbor algorithm

Route	Algorithm's Node of Nearest Neighbour
1	O-15-19-11-O
2	O-12-18-13-17-O
3	O-14-10-5-6-O
4	O-16-4-8-O
5	O-7-9-O
6	O-3-2-1-O

As seen on Table 5 it can be seen that 6 delivery routes are obtained with a total distance of 1551,5 kilometers. Assuming the price of fuel is Rp 9.500 per liter, thus the fuel needed is 155,15 liters, and the fuel cost expended using this method is Rp. 1.473.925, factoring in labor costs, the total expended using this method is Rp 8.873.925.

Route Development using Cluster First-Route Second Method

To determine a route in the Cluster First-Route Second method, select hospitals with the shortest distance obtained from Google Maps with a maximum vehicle capacity of 123 box on every route.

Figure 2. Route Development

Cataract lens delivery route determination using the Cluster First-Route Second method can be seen in the table below:

Table 7. Route development using Cluster First-Route Second method

Route	Track	Box Quantity	Distance (km)
1	G-1-3-2-G	103	43.5
2	G-9-7-G	113	252
3	G-8-5-13-14-G	118	323
4	G-17-16-19-G	120	317
5	G-18-15-10-6-G	118	293.7
6	G-12-11-4-G	119	299
Total		691	1528.2

It is seen in Table 7 that 6 routes are obtained with total delivery distance of 1528.2 kilometers. Assuming the price of fuel is Rp 9.500 per liter, the total fuel required is 152.82 liters, and the fuel cost expended by using this method is Rp. 1.451.790 factoring in labor costs, the total cost expended using this method is Rp 8.851.790.

Comparison of cataract lens distribution route determination distribusi Lensa Katarak before data processing is done using the saving matrix method and cluster first route second method, and after data processing using the methods mentioned are carried out can be seen in Table 8 below.

Table 8. Route Comparison

No	Method	Route Count	Distance	Total Cost
1	Before Optimization	19	4256	Rp 18,843,200.00
2	Saving Matrik	6	1551.5	Rp 8,873,925.00
3	Cluster First Route Second	6	1528.2	Rp 8,851,790.00

After comparing the results between these 2 methods before data processing is done are known, the cost and distance efficiency that the company achieved can be seen in Table 9 below:

Table 9. Cost and Distance Efficiency

No	Method	Distance Saving		Cost Saving	
1	Saving Matrik	2704.5	63.55%	Rp 9,969,275.00	52.90%
2	Cluster First Route Second	2727.8	64.09%	Rp 9,991,410.00	53.02%

CONCLUSION

Based on calculations and data comparisons done, the chosen method of determining a route for the distribution of Cataract Lenses is the Cluster First Route Second method. This method is chosen because it has the shortest distance for product delivery from the distribution Center in Padalarang, West Java to the select hospitals in West Java and DKI Jakarta. This short travel distance means that the company spends less on delivery cost, as the shorter distance means less fuel is consumed, thus the savings.

The delivery distance using the *Cluster First Route Second* method is 1528,2 kilometers, one liter of fuel (dexlite) used by a vehicle can travel 10 kilometers, with a distance of 1528,2 the fuel needed is 152,82 liters. Assuming the current price of dexlite is Rp 9.500, the total cost of fuel amounts to Rp 1.451.790 by factoring in labor costs, the total cost expended using the Cluster First-Route Second method is Rp 8.851.790 each month. The results from the Saving Matrix and Cluster First Route Second method can be used to schedule delivery by maximizing the vehicle capacity to carry the products to several destination locations.

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